

Critical Review of Performance Analysis of a Shell & Tube Heat Exchanger Employing Tubes of Various Cross-Sections Through CFD Analysis

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Abstract: Shell & Tube heat exchangers are widely utilized in various industries as a popular type of heat exchanger. These are employed due to their distinct benefits. These heat exchangers are used to reclaim the heat that would otherwise be wasted. The current research is centred on doing a comprehensive assessment of existing studies worldwide in the field of heat exchangers. Multiple studies have consistently shown that academics have prioritized improving the efficiency of heat exchangers. To enhance performance, conventional heat exchangers undergo many types of changes. Modifications in heat exchangers involve the implementation of baffles, alterations in the cross-sections of tubes, and adjustments in baffle cut and spacing. The researchers deduce that all of these alterations augment the thermal conductivity across the heat exchangers.

Keywords: Shell & Tube heat exchangers, Heat recovery, baffles, baffle cut & baffle spacing.

I. Introduction

For mechanical engineering, each component requires certain working conditions in order to achieve optimal efficiency. In most industrial processes, a significant amount of energy is wasted in the form of heat. To address this issue, several procedures are implemented to recover a portion, or perhaps the majority, of this waste heat energy. During such circumstances, a specialized device called a heat exchanger is utilized. These heat exchangers extract thermal energy from one source and transfer it to another source. Recently, researchers have been investigating several factors that can optimize the process of heat exchange.

A heat exchanger is a system in which heat is transferred from one fluid to another fluid. Heat exchangers have the capability to be employed in both the process of heating and cooling. Fluids are segregated by a physical barrier to avoid their intermingling. Alternatively, in certain situations, the fluids may be in direct contact with each other. These heat exchangers are mostly utilized in sewage treatment, natural-gas processing, petroleum refineries, petrochemical plants, power stations, chemical plants, refrigeration, air conditioning, and space heating.

Fig. 1 Simple arrangement of a Heat Exchangers

Shell & Tube heat exchangers consist of many tubes enclosed within a hollow shell. The tubes and shell both contain fluids, with the tubes containing the hot fluid and the shell containing

the cool fluid, and vice versa. The collection of tubes is referred to as a Tube Bundle, and they might have different types of cross-sectional areas. These tubes can have longitudinal fins or be plain. These heat exchangers are specifically designed for usage in situations where there is a high level of pressure.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) refers to the examination of fluid flows through the utilization of numerical techniques for solving equations. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) allows for the analysis of intricate issues that include the interaction of fluids with other fluids, solids, or gases. CFD analyses are commonly employed in engineering domains such as aerodynamics and hydrodynamics. These analyses allow for the determination of important quantities including lift, drag, and field properties such as pressures and velocities. Fluid dynamics deals with the application of partial differential equations to describe physical phenomena. Advanced computational fluid dynamics (CFD) solvers convert these physical rules into algebraic equations and can effectively solve them using numerical methods.

II. Literature Review

Abhishek Agarwal (2021) investigated the application of a plate heat exchanger in case of cooling of engine oil. Heat exchangers are used for various industrial application for transfer of enthalpy from hot fluid to cold. One of them is Plate Heat Exchanger which finds its application in evaporating systems. The compactness, high effectiveness and easy maintenance of Plate Heat Exchanger makes it best choice for process industries. The current research investigates the application of Plate Heat Exchanger in cooling of engine oil using techniques of Computational Fluid Dynamics for low, medium and high Reynolds number using ANSYS CFX software. The CAD model is developed using Creo design software and turbulence model used for analysis is RNG k-epsilon which gives good predictions for complex flows involving swirls. The CFD

analysis is conducted for different values of Reynolds number. The temperature distribution, effectiveness and overall heat transfer coefficient is determined for different values of Reynolds number.

Ahmad Hanan et al. (2021) conducted a performance analysis of a heat exchanger. Heat exchangers have found extensive applications in the engineering sector owing to the crucial need for heat transfer and temperature regulation in the process industry. The performance analysis of a heat exchanger can either be investigated experimentally or utilizing computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The simulation of flow conditions based on CFD principles is considered as a contemporary approach for conducting performance analysis and design optimization of the heat exchanger. The paper aims to present how the performance optimization parameters of shell and tube heat exchanger effect its performance in terms of the extent of heat transfer achieved and fall in the shell outlet temperature. A standard model (Model 1) was initially defined, and seven subsequent models were created with one varying parameter as compared to Model 1 to carry out the comparative analysis. The results showed that decrease in inlet velocity, increase in thermal conductivity of the heat exchanger material, reduction in baffle spacing and use of triangular tube bundle arrangement has significant influence on the reduction of the condensate temperature. The effects of the same parameters on the temperature distribution and heat transfer rate have also been discussed.

Ahmet Aydin et al. (2020) conducted an optimization of heat exchanger based on total cost (initial costing as well as operation costing). After optimization, flow analysis has been conducted to predict temperature pattern & flow field. CFD analysis is performed for flow analysis. Experimental as well as CFD analysis results are compared with each other. It has been confirmed that baffles significantly affect the overall performance. New baffle design creates lower pressure drop.

Amol Niphade et al. (2015) analysed and designed an ingenious heat exchanger specifically for dairy applications. For the purpose a shell and tube heat exchanger has been designed so that nearly five thousand litres milk can be supported per day. In order to analyse the situation ANSYS Fluent led CFD analysis & mathematical model-based analysis both have been applied.

Arpit Thakur et al. (2015) analysed about an EAHX (Earth to Air Heat Exchanger) which can be effectively used for conditioning of buildings. Air has been employed as the transferring medium in the current research study. Analysis has been conducted for dry & hot weather conditions where ambient temperature has been taken as 319K. CFD analysis has been performed for the current case. Thermal conductivity of soil has been taken as $4 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, model dimensions are 60m length & having a diameter of 100 mm. 239 fins having 250 mm pitch are being used. This fin model achieves 20.5°C whereas finless model achieves 17.7°C of temperature drop.

Avinash D Jadhav et al. (2014) conducted a numerical analysis in order to evaluate the impact of shell diameter, baffle cut & baffle spacing on the design of shell side. For designing purpose flow & temperature fields have been evaluated using CFD analysis being performed through ANSYS software. Pressure drop, outlet temperature & heat transfer has been calculated using Bell–Delaware method.

Avinash P. Shinde et al. (2018) investigated about improving the efficiency of a shell and tube heat exchanger by varying the cross section of tubes. Model of the heat exchanger has been developed in Solidworks 2018. ANSYS 18.0 software has been used to conduct the CFD analysis. Different cross-sections to be used in this current research are square, square with fillet & hexagonal cross-sections. Results of the comparative study reveal that tubes having hexagonal cross-sections transfers most amount of heat across the fluids.

C Rajesh Babu et al. (2015) studied about enhancing the performance of a heat exchanger by using inserts in the heat exchanger. For the purpose a heat exchanger having concentric tubes with and without inserts has been analysed. For conducting CFD analysis, ANSYS 14.5 software has been employed.

G. S. L. Swathi et al. (2014) analysed a heat exchanger on the basis of two different materials aluminium & copper. Heat transfer rate enhancement is the primary aim of the current research. Geometry of the heat exchanger has been developed using Gambit and CFD analysis has been performed using a K- ϵ model using ANSYS Fluent. Temperature, pressure and velocity distributions have been drawn in order to conduct the analysis.

G. Nivedini et al. (2020) compared the experimental & CFD analysis results when nanofluids are used in heat exchangers so that transfer of thermal energy is improved across the exchanger. Silica nanoparticles are used in the current research. Only the conventional fluid is replaced by nano particles. A double pipe heat exchanger is used and CFD analysis is conducted in ANSYS. 10°C improvement in temperature is achieved when silica nano particles are used in place of conventional fluid.

Gurbir Singh et al. (2014) analysed a shell and tube heat exchanger where water has been considered as the working fluid. Hot water flows inside the tubes whereas cold water flows outside the tubes. CFD Analysis has been conducted using ANSYS 13.0. Model has been developed in Solidworks. For the analysis purpose Velocity, temperature & pressure contours have been calculated.

K. Ravikumar et al. (2017) evaluated the performance of fin tube exchanger for different fin thicknesses. This analysis is performed as the effectiveness and efficiency of any heat exchanger are two of the most important parameters when considering design field. Analysis has been performed in two ways- one by using correlations & second by using ANSYS CFX. Analysis in CFX reveals that software simulation offers specific benefits whenever some design modifications are required. A 3D geometry of fin type tube heat exchanger is developed and analysed through CFD analysis.

Liliana Dumitrescu et al. (2021) conducted a CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) analysis on a heat exchanger of gas-liquid type which is fitted on gasification component. In order to analyze the heat exchanger, Solidworks software is employed which can be used to study the flow simulation problems. Temperature & flow patterns have been drawn with the help of this software in order to study the current research. The system transfers heat from flue gases which have been generated by gasification system to the liquid medium. This is

further sent to a secondary heat exchanger which is used to heat the water from boilers.

M. Satish Kumar et al. (2017) studied about the impact of baffle design on pressure drop across the heat exchanger. Shell & tube heat exchanger has been used for the current analysis. Different shapes of baffles have been designed in order to compare their effect on pressure drop. Different shapes to be compared are helical baffles, segmental baffles & these two are compared with the performance of a heat exchanger which is not having baffles. Heat exchanger has been developed in CATIA V5 & for the analysis purpose, ANSYS 15.0 is employed. Experimental as well as simulation results reveal that helical baffles are of most importance as they can achieve effective pressure drop of 0.17134 Pa. If further enhancement in pressure drop is required, helical baffles may be updated & modified and used in shell & tube heat exchangers.

Mahendra Kumar Verma et al. (2020) evaluated the thermal performance for an EAPHE (Earth-Air-Pipe-Heat-Exchanger) in transient condition when helical air pipes are used. Thermal performance of the system weakens in long term because of sub soil saturation. CFD analysis is conducted using ANSYS Fluent 19.0. Aluminium water pipe arrangement represents continuous effectiveness of 0.76 after running the heat exchanger for 36 hours.

Md Imran Pasha et al. (2020) studied about double pipe heat exchangers for different materials. Current research specifically focused on the heat exchangers used in cryogenic applications. Heat exchangers have been designed in CATIA, CFD analysis has been performed in ANSYS. Heat exchangers have been analysed for different materials like copper, aluminium & steel.

Mohammed Irshad et al. (2017) analysed about shell and tube heat exchangers for different types of segmental baffles. For the analysis purpose, different types of segmental baffle assemblies are designed & fitted with heat exchanger. ANSYS 14.5 software has been employed in order to analyse the heat exchanger. Heat exchanger to be designed contains 7 tubes of 600 mm length while the shell diameter remains at 90 mm. In order to analyse the heat exchanger, velocity, pressure & temperature profiles have been evaluated for different baffle orientations.

Muhammad Mahmood Aslam Bhutta et al. (2012) reviewed the applications of CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) on the heat exchangers. Various researches have shown that CFD analysis has found their way in analysing about thermal response, pressure drop, velocity, temperature distribution etc. Various researches have employed K- ϵ model. Various researches have revealed that these CFD analyses have proven to be efficient tool in predicting the performance and behaviour of heat exchangers.

Mukkerla Hemanth et al. (2017) analysed the impact of using different types of NANO fluids when mixed with water taken as base fluid on the performance of shell and tube heat exchanger. For analysis purpose, a comparative study is performed with baffles and without baffles. Baffles to be used are of helical shape. NANO fluids to be employed are Titanium carbide & Aluminium Oxide. Two volume fractions have been employed of 0.4 & 0.5. Different properties of NANO fluids are being used

as inlet parameters & has been calculated theoretically. 3D geometry of the heat exchanger has been created using Creo software & ANSYS has been employed to conduct the CFD analysis.

P.C. Mukesh Kumar et al. (2019) investigated the heat transfer and pressure drop for a double helical coiled tube heat exchanger which handles water/MWCNT nanoparticles. For analysis purpose ANSYS 14.5 has been employed. Analysis has been conducted for a range of Dean number of 1300-2200 under the conditions of laminar flow. Heat exchanger has been modelled in Creo 2.0. Nanofluids at different volume concentrations of 0.6%, 0.4% & 0.2 % have been taken into consideration. Simulation data has been compared with experimental results. At 1400 Dean number, 0.6% volume fraction has 30% larger Nusselt number than water.

P.S. Aswin et al. (2021) analysed the shell & tube type heat exchanger with the help of ANSYS. Here tubes are placed inside the shell. Hot water flows through tubes and cold-water flows through the shell. In order to analyze the system stream line flow, velocity & heat transfer through the fluids is being studied. Two different cases have been considered in this analysis. One case being the heat exchanger along with baffles & the other case being the heat exchanger without baffles. Certainly, the system where baffles are employed along with heat exchangers provides greater amount of heat transfer.

Palash Goya et al. (2018) analyzed heat transfer for a tube in tube helically coiled type heat exchanger. Fluid in both types of tubes have been varied in order to observe the effect on heat transfer of these type of heat exchangers. Helical tubes are constructed by copper & the fluid has been taken as water. Total heat transfer has been evaluated with the help of CFD analysis being conducted through ANSYS Fluent 16.0.

Perone C. et al. (2021) conducted a CFD analysis on a tubular type heat exchanger to be used for the conditioning of olive paste so that the process of extraction of olive oil is improved. This analysis as intended for better understanding of impact of inlet situations of olive paste on hydrodynamic and thermal behaviour. The CFD analysis is performed on Solidworks-2016. Tube in tube model of heat exchanger has been used in the current analysis here inner tube contains olive paste & jacket contains hot water. Pressure drop and heat transfer were calculated by varying mass flow rate & the temperature of inlet.

Petrik M. et al. (2018) numerically investigated a shell and tube heat exchanger having horizontal baffles and compared the results with SC-Tetra V11. Shell & tube heat exchanger has been compared for two separate conditions- with baffles and without baffles. Current research investigates the impact of baffle types, space between baffles & baffle cut on the heat transfer across the heat exchanger.

Pramod Deshmukh et al. (2016) analysed about helical coiled tube heat exchanger for its performance having counterflow arrangement. Temperature profiles are used to analyse the heat exchanger in current research. For analysis purpose ANSYS 15.0 software has been utilised.

R. Maradona et al. (2015) investigated about possible solutions for the enhancement of heat transfer rate without applying any

external power source. Helical tubes have been developed for the purpose. Impact of tube diameter, pitch & pitch coil diameter on nature of flow of fluid across the heat exchanger has been studied by using CFD analysis. Varying Reynolds number has also been used as the inlet parameter. Velocity & temperature distribution have been drawn in order to analyse the situation. Heat transfer coefficient & Nusselt number have been estimated.

Rahul Singh et al. (2016) analysed shell and tube heat exchangers with the aid of CFD analysis. Water has been used as the working fluid for the current research. Primary aim of the research is to analyse the impact of flow variations on the heat transfer. For the analysis purpose two types of flow patterns have been used which are counter flow and parallel flow. 3D model of the shell & tube heat exchanger has been developed using Inventor professional software which is developed by American firm Autodesk. For the analysis purpose ANSYS 14.5 tool has been employed. Circular shape fins have been used in the current research. Shell dimension is 400 mm within which 7 tubes, 4 baffles and 84 fins have also been employed. Results reveal that these arrangements have bettered the performance of heat exchangers. Results also reveal that the arrangement having circular fins, counter flow pattern & baffles provides best possible results.

Ram Kishan et al. (2020) examined the temperature and flow fields for box and tube heat exchangers wherein different types of tube patterns have been used. ANSYS 14.0 software is used for analysis conduction. Three different types of heat exchangers are used in the current study. Impact of tube width on temperature has been discussed using CFD analysis.

Ramkrishna Gondane et al. (2018) studied about improving the capability of heat transfer of a shell and tube heat exchanger by using different type of geometries for tubes using ANSYS Fluent. In order to improve the performance, corrugated type tubes are employed instead of plain tubes. Both the tubes are compared for their heat transfer coefficient.

S. Elangovan et al. (2021) conducted an CFD analysis of a monolithic type heat exchanger so that heat transfer is increased by varying material & shape of air passage. Different shapes of air passage used are oval, hexagonal & circular. Materials used are CrCO_3 , Al_2O_3 & SiC ceramic materials. ANSYS Fluent is used for analysis purpose after modelling the heat exchanger in CATIA.

Sachin k. Patel et al. (2015) reviewed the researchers conducted by numerous researchers in the field of shell and tube heat exchangers. These heat exchangers have been mostly optimized in order to enhance the performance of the heat exchanger. Optimization has been performed on the basis of effectiveness calculated in different conditions. Current research study concludes that mostly the researchers have used baffle angle, pitch length, mass flow rate & diameter of tube in order to analyse their impact on the temperature difference achieved in different situations.

Shubham Sharma et al. (2021) compared the performance of heat transfer for two STHXs (Shell & tube heat exchangers) having different arrangements of tubes. 21 & 24 tubes are arranged in staggered grid and inline arrangement. Staggered arrangement is seen to be providing lesser amount of thermal

stratification. Mass flow rate of shell side liquid is varied from 0.5 kg/s to 0.1 kg/s and tube side liquid mass flow rate is kept constant at 0.25kg/s. Pressure drop, effectiveness & heat transfer efficiency have been analysed. 0.1 kg/s of mass flow rate causes minimum pressure drop

Shuvam Mohanty et al. (2020) investigated a STE (Shell & Tube Heat Exchangers) for effectiveness having 50% baffle cuts & varying the number of baffles. Water has been used as the working fluid in the current research. Counterflow arrangement has been used for flow of fluids. ANSYS 14.0 has been used to conduct the CFD analysis. Various input parameters to be used are baffle spacing, baffle cut & their impact on pressure drop & heat transfer has been studied. In this investigation, a comprehensive approach is established in detail to analyse the effectiveness of the shell and tube heat exchanger (STE) with 50% baffle cuts (Bc) with varying number of baffles. CFD simulations were conducted on a single pass and single tube heat exchanger (HE) using water as working fluid. A counterflow technique is implemented for this simulation study. Modified model design yields a 44% of reduction in pressure drop & 60.66% increase in heat transfer.

Sugin Elankavi R et al. (2018) analysed a shell & tube heat exchanger having single segmented group of baffles using Simulation CFD 2015 software that is developed by Autodesk company. Experimental results have been compared with simulation results. It has been observed that using a series of baffles considerable amount of heat transfer can be increased.

Tejas Patil et al. (2022) The shell and tube unit is a highly used heat exchanger in industrial processes. This study employed a shell and tube heat exchanger equipped with helical and double segmental baffles. An analysis is conducted on a shell and tube heat exchanger using ANSYS 2021 to discover the optimal heat transfer coefficient and minimize pressure loss by modifying the spacing between baffles, the number of baffles, and the form of the tube cross-section. Various tubes with different cross-sections, such as round, elliptical in the horizontal and vertical planes, and angled at 30° , 45° , and 60° , were also examined. The results have been determined to be influenced by the type of baffle, the spacing between baffles, and the form of the cross-sectional tube.

An investigation was conducted on a shell and tube heat exchanger equipped with double segmental and helical baffles, with Reynolds numbers ranging from 10000 to 40000. The fluid in the hot tube was kept at a constant velocity of 0.01 m/s. Conversely, the velocity of the Cold Shell fluid varied based on the Reynolds number. The initial temperature of the cold fluid was 300.15 K, while the initial temperature of the hot fluid was 353.15 K. The configuration of eight helical baffles within a vertically oriented elliptical tube was found to provide the highest overall heat transfer coefficient. Vertical elliptical tube geometry demonstrates superior performance when compared to alternative tube geometries, particularly when used in conjunction with both double-segmental and helical baffles. Helical baffles exhibit superior heat transfer capabilities in comparison to double-segmental baffles.

While helical and double-segmental baffles enhance the efficiency of vertical elliptical tubes, they also result in the highest pressure drop. Maximum pressure loss signifies the requirement for additional pumping power to maintain the fluid's

current velocity. Angled elliptical tubes are optimal for achieving a harmonious equilibrium between heat transfer and pressure decrease. They possess a significantly reduced pressure drop compared to other tube shapes with different cross-sections and demonstrate heat transfer capabilities that are similar to those of vertical elliptical tubes.

Yamini Y. Pawar et al. (2017) investigated the impact of different coil geometries on heat transfer (convective type) with the use of CFD analysis. Three different types of coils have been used in the current research and these are spiral, conical & helical coils. Tubes of 3000 mm length having thickness of 1.5 mm & internal diameter of 9.5 mm. analysis has been conducted for three different flow rates of 25 LPH, 20 LPH & 15 LPH. Comparative research of all the inlet parameters represents that when helical coils are used, heat transfer rate is maximum & 9.54% more than other two type of coils. Nusselt number is being observed to be increasing along with increasing the mass flow rate. Experiments have also been conducted for given inlet parameters and the results of experimental study is duly aligned with CFD analysis results.

Yuvraj Singh Rajput et al. (2019) investigated about temperature gradient & heat transfer in a heat exchanger having counterflow arrangement for various fin thickness. CFD analysis has been conducted on the basis of FVM (Finite Volume Method). Inlet air velocity has been taken as 4, 3, 2 & 1 m/s & volume flow rate has been kept at 6, 5, 4, 3 & 2 L/min. Temperature of tube side fluid has been kept at 80, 70, 60 & 50°C. Results reveal that for a 3 mm fin heat transfer increases by 15%.

III. Conclusions

The current research has evaluated several earlier research works. The majority of the conducted studies have concentrated on enhancing the efficiency of the heat exchangers. The current research has yielded some notable findings, which can be summarized as follows-

- Heat exchangers are widely used mechanical devices for efficiently recovering waste heat in various engineering applications.
- The majority of research in the field of heat exchangers focuses on improving their performance.
- Various adjustments are being made to heat exchangers in order to improve their performance.
- Modifications to heat exchangers are mostly achieved by the utilization of baffles and the implementation of various tube cross-sections. These modifications effectively enhance the overall performance of the heat exchangers.

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